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Volatile nitrosamine manual stack monitoring method: sampling validation and performance assessment on stack simulated conditions

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ABSTRACT

Degradation products of sorbent amines used in Post Combustion CO₂ Capture (PCC) (amines, nitrosamines, etc.) are potentially emitted to the atmosphere, impacting health and the environment. This paper proposes and validates for the first time a manual stack sampling method for monitoring nitrosamine emissions, using a purpose-built test bench and simulating nitrosamine sampling through monitoring tests under controlled conditions mimicking those of a PCC plant. The method uses isokinetic sampling (due to the presence of water droplets in the PCC flue gas), a combination of liquid sampling (three impingers in series) and dry sampling cartridges. Collected samples were refrigerated and sent to for laboratory analysis (using a Gas Chromatography - Thermal Energy Analyser). In terms of the recovered mass of the target analytes, the method was successfully validated for the five more volatile compounds (NDMA, NMEA, NDEA, NDPA, and NPIP), while the three less volatile nitrosamine's (NDBA, NPYR, and NMOR) had recoveries of 75–80 %. However, based on the same experimental data but using the criterion of recovering in the last impinger <5 % of the total (for each species), only the linear nitrosamines with medium volatility failed, NDPA and NDBA, capturing 11 and 22 % respectively. As expected, these last two nitrosamines were also found in sizeable amounts in the back-end cartridge, demonstrating significant breakthrough from all the impingers. In spite of the general good recovery of the method for volatile nitrosamines, the results for some of the semi-volatile species show that is advisable to enhance the method to achieve a recovery closer to 100 % for all the nitrosamines. Two simple proposals to achieve that goal are discussed. The sampling recovery depends on the volatility and chemical structure of the specific nitrosamines. The conclusions presented here could be carefully extrapolated to other species with similar volatilities and structures, but not to low volatile nitrosamines which will require different sample media to be sampled, for that reason they are outside of the scope of this work.

Glossary

Acronym	Name	CAS #
MEA	Monoethanolamine	141–43–5
DEA	Diethanolamine	111–42–2
MMEA	Methylmonoethanolamine	109–83–1
MDEA	Methyldiethanolamine	105–59–9

Note: All other compounds are included in Table 1.

1. Introduction

Within current Carbon Capture technologies, the most widely implemented method for Post Combustion CO₂ Capture (PCC) is chemical absorption into organic solvents, with amine-based solvents

being the most common choice. Amongst other amines, monoethanolamine (MEA) has been traditionally used for decades to remove acid gases containing H₂S and CO₂ in oil refining operations and gas sweetening (Kohl and Nielsen, 1997; Stewart, 2014; Pantelis and Tsiourva, 2017).

In the last two decades, there has been a renewed interest in this technology for use in PCC plants for Carbon Capture Usage and Storage (CCUS), in the frame of Net Zero emissions policies. In the effort to reduce the impact of fossil fuels, PCC using amine-based technology has been used in several power stations and natural gas processing facilities around the world, becoming the most common and widely used method. In these applications, the most commonly used amine is MEA, which is a primary amine and a primary alcohol. However, under PCC conditions the solvent amines slowly degrade producing several breakdown

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products, with the nitrosamines the most concerning of them, due to its toxicity and carcinogenicity. In fact, nitrosamine emissions have been identified and recognized as a potential health and safety risk of CO₂ capture by amine scrubbing (Rochelle, 2024).

This paper summarises the relevant information on the nitrosamines of interest and the typical PCC plants' process conditions impacting their atmospheric emissions. It is well known that in the PCC process the temperature of the flue gas is relatively low (to maximize the CO₂ absorption) (Meekoch and Maneintr, 2020), producing water saturation, and condensed water droplets as a secondary undesired result. Due to this, both manual and instrumental methods require isokinetic sampling to obtain representative samples. This is particularly important in the case of nitrosamines, amines and other pollutants potentially being absorbed in the water droplets.

Most of the reported monitoring of volatile nitrosamine emissions in PCC pilot plants has been undertaken using variations of the water impinger manual sampling method, using sulfamic acid (generally at 0.1 M) to prevent further nitrosation of the amines also present within the samples (potentially adding newly formed nitrosamines to the sample). Furthermore, a previous work organised two international round robins on the analysis of 9 nitrosamines in traced solvent matrices and sampled atmospheric emissions from a PCC pilot plant (Fraboulet et al., 2016). However, up to the best of our knowledge no single validation of these manual sampling methods has been reported, and generally the different authors report the findings with no mention of the sampling recoveries. Then, the reported emission levels rely on the assumption that sampling recovery was 100 %.

This paper focuses primarily on nitrosamines, due to their toxicity and due to the need to develop, test and validate methods that can be made available for these substances (standardised and validated sampling procedures compatible with the existing analytical measuring standardised methods). We report the validation of a method for volatile nitrosamines manual monitoring applicable to PCCs. We describe the candidate methods for nitrosamines sampling, for which no reference methods are yet available. Also, this work contains a summary of the research conducted and the resolutions to the problems which were encountered. Sample management was studied, considering the possible issues related with the integrity of the samples in all the stages of the process (sampling, storage, handling and shipping prior lab analysis).

A purpose made scaled-down test bench was designed and assembled, where the experiments were undertaken using a mix of gases (air, CO, NO_x, SO₂ and water vapour) replicating common PCC conditions and containing trace but still measurable concentrations of nitrosamines. A validation of the system to ensure its appropriate functioning was performed which included assessing reproducibility of the programmed synthetic mixed flows, homogenisation times and stability measurements. Safety related aspects including gas line leaks checks, final capture devices to contain all the nitrosamines amounts after each test, safe storage or dilution of pollutants within waste gases for final disposition, and safe work, contingencies and emergencies protocols were also addressed. The latter is essential due to the well-known carcinogenic character of the nitrosamines intended to be used during the tests (Beard and Swager, 2021). The proposed and tested nitrosamine monitoring manual method resulted from the adaptation and enhancement of previous proposals after a comprehensive review of current scientific and technical literature and the analysis of the available (pre-existing) sampling and measuring techniques.

2. Nitrosamine potential emissions in PCC

2.1. Nitrosamine species present in PCC pilot plants

There is a special interest in the by-products generated from the breakdown of the amine solvents, which can nitrosate forming potentially carcinogenic nitrosamines. Under typical PCC conditions, nitrosation is a process affecting all amines used at industrial scale, such as

MEA, DEA, MMEA, MDEA, PZ, etc. Despite the diversity and complexity of the different existing degradation channels (thermal, oxidation, catalysed by corrosion, etc.), and the attempts to reduce them, all PCC processes will lead eventually to nitrosation and nitrosamine formation.

Therefore, PCC emissions have the potential to generate environmental and health risk concerns if they were to contain toxics or hazardous pollutants (Azzi and White, 2016). It has been shown that within systematic experiments, nitrosamine formation yield is proportional to the concentration of common secondary amines generated by MEA degradation (such as HEGly, HEEDA and DEA) and it is a function of CO₂ loading and temperature (Fine et al., 2014; Meekoch and Maneintr, 2020).

In general, amine emissions should also be considered since they would potentially impact the sample stability. This is due to the potential further nitrosation of amines, as other exhaust components (nitrogen species as nitrites or acids) can react with amines to produce more nitrosamines. On the other hand, amines are also likely to have a detrimental effect on the environment due to their low rate of biodegradation and high toxicity and/or carcinogenic character of several species (Eide-Haugmo et al., 2009), however, this is beyond of the scope of this work.

A similar situation will occur with the case of nitramines, which is advisable to be addressed in future works, although their toxicity (specifically their mutagenicity) is low compared to their corresponding analogous nitrosamines. In fact, in many cases nitrosamines are approximately 15 times more mutagenic than their N-nitramine analogues (Wagner et al., 2014). However, nitramines are photolytically stable, so in principle they could be preserved in the environment longer than nitrosamines.

There is a large list of literature on solvent amine degradation, some of which includes nitrosamines. For instance, a recent review of the degradation and emissions in 18 different PCC pilot plants and 29 individual campaigns showed that the degree of the degradation of an amine (or reciprocally the solvent stability) varies with several operational parameters. The authors also demonstrated that the total liquid-phase heat stable salt concentration and the gas phase ammonia concentration are the most useful parameters to obtain information of the state and overall degradation of the solvent (Buvik et al., 2021), although this information is not enough to infer the amount or type of the produced nitrosamines.

With the focus on nitrosamines, we have reviewed >250 references, and we have identified at least 20 nitrosamines already measured in PCC, these have been reported (at least) within 30 documents produced in the last 20+ years. Table 1 summarises these findings.

The selected species resulted from comprehensive literature research focused on identifying the nitrosamines already identified in pilot plants and laboratory scale studies. Worth mentioning that a large set of papers and other documents employing chemical modelling strategies include many other species, however, none of these are included in this report (unless it was identified in practice). Some nitrosamines are reported more than others, such as NDMA or NDELA. This is not necessarily indicative of a higher probability of their occurrence in PCC, rather that these species were selected to be measured beforehand. Only a few of the cited works performed a full spectroscopic survey to determine which nitrosamines species were present in the PCC (solvent or emissions, pilot plants or lab scale facilities) before quantifying the target analytes.

In Table 1 species are organised by vapour pressure, from low to high, i.e. more volatile nitrosamines are in the top of the table. Most used acronyms are included. Hereafter only the first abbreviation will be used. MNPZ is called NPZ in some documents, this is disadvised since this abbreviation is also used for the corresponding nitramine. The acronym Nitro-4MNPZ is introduced here since no abbreviation was available in the literature. Here, "linear" type nitrosamines refer to compounds including both, linear and bent structures, single or even branched structures. On the other hand, "ring" type nitrosamines are species which includes a ring (hexagonal or pentagonal) in their

Table 1
Nitrosamine species measured in PCC.

Acronym.	Nitrosamine name	CAS #	Formula	Mass [g/mol]	Structure	Additional functional groups
TONO	Total Nitrosamines	-	-	-	-	-
NDMA	N-Nitrosodimethylamine	62-75-9*	C2H6N2O	74	Linear	-
NMEA	N-Nitroso-Methyl-Ethylamine	10,595-95-6*	C3H8N2O	88	Linear	-
NDEA	N-Nitrosodiethylamine	55-18-5*	C4H10N2O3	102	Linear	-
NDiPA	N-Nitrosodi-isopropylamine	601-77-4	C6H14N2O	130	Linear	-
NDPA	N-Nitrosodipropylamine	621-64-7*	C6H14N2O	130	Linear	-
NMOx	N-nitroso-2-methyl-oxazolidine	39,884-53-2	C4H8N2O2	116	Ring (5)	Oxide
NPIP	N-Nitrosopiperidine	100-75-4*	C5H10N2O	114	Ring (6)	-
NDBA	N-Nitrosodi-n-butylamine	924-16-3*	C8H18N2O	158	Linear	-
NDIBA	N-Nitrosodi-isobutylamine	997-95-5	C8H18N2O	158	Linear	-
NPYR	N-Nitrosopyrrolidine	930-55-2*	C4H8N2O	100	Ring (5)	-
NMOR / NSMO	N-Nitrosomorpholine	59-89-2*	C4H8N2O2	116	Ring (6)	Oxide
MNPZ (NPZ)	N-nitrosopiperazine	5632-47-3*	C4H9N3O	115	Ring (6)	Amine
EHEN / NEELA	Ethylethanolnitrosamine	13,147-25-6	C4H10N2O2	118	Linear	Alcohol
NMELA	2-(Methylnitrosamino)ethanol	26,921-68-6	C3H8N2O2	104	Linear	Alcohol
NDELA	N-Nitrosodiethanolamine	1116-54-7*	C4H10N2O3	134	Linear	Alcohol x2
DNPPZ / DNPIPA	N,N'-Dinitrosopiperazine	140-79-4*	C4H8N4O2	114	Ring (6)	Nitrosamine x2
NHEGly	Nitroso-(2-hydroxyethyl)-glycine	80,556-89-4*	C4H8N2O4	148	Linear	Glycine, Alcohol
NDiNA	N,N-bis(3,5,5-trimethylhexyl)nitrous amide	1207,995-62-7	C18H38N2O	299	Linear	-
PZE-NO	4-Nitroso-1-piperazineethanol	48,121-20-6*	C6H13N3O2	159	Ring (6)	Alcohol
Nitro-4MNPZ	1-nitro-4-nitrosopiperazine	107,938-05-6	C4H8N4O3	160	Ring (6)	Nitramine

Note: nitrosamines used in this work are highlighted in **bold** letters.

structure, just being a ring or a ring with some additional branches.

The thirteen nitrosamines highlighted with * (Table 1) have been included in a recent report on health effects of amines and their derivatives associated to PCC (Svendensen et al., 2023). Their criterium for selecting those nitrosamines was restricting the search to publications on genotoxicity and carcinogenicity. Furthermore, the other seven nitrosamines are known to be toxic, irritant, mutagenic, carcinogenic and/or hepatotoxins. It means that the whole group of nitrosamines identified in PCC are potential hazardous pollutants.

The eight nitrosamine species used in the test series to validate the manual monitoring method proposed in this work, have been selected since they are volatile nitrosamines, covering the range of the first twelve species in the list. These nitrosamines are included in the reference standard material EPA 8270/Appendix IX Nitrosamines Mix, which was selected for this validation test since working with one single solution reduces the sources of experimental uncertainty. Finally, they were selected as there are certified analytical methods in place to measure the sampled aqueous solutions and the dry cartridges for all these species.

2.2. Measured values of nitrosamine emissions in PCC

There is little publicly available information on nitrosamine emission levels from PCC plants. In Table 2 all the measured nitrosamine emission values found in the literature are shown, which range from 0.01 to 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. No reference limit for nitrosamine emissions has been officially established or agreed by the scientific community, therefore some reference values related to different limits are included in the Table 3.

There are several papers and project reports attempting measuring nitrosamine emissions from PCC plants. However, most of them report only lower than detection limits (LDL). Those works are not mentioned here, neither the nitrosamines reported below the detection limits of the used analytical method. Generally, the manual sampling methods use a particular configuration of impingers with water as absorption media, in most cases adding sulfamic acid to avoid further nitrosation within the samples. However, the sampling recovery or collection efficiency is not mentioned in any of the found works, implicitly assuming that this recovery is 100 %. One paper explicitly recognizes that the sampling method requires the determination of the collection efficiency (Fraboulet et al., 2014), but during the evaluation of the used method the authors found that their second impinger collected nearly 20 % of the measured NDMA (instead the expected value of <5 %), suggesting

Table 2

Nitrosamines emissions from PCC plants, reported values.

Site / PCC plant	Year	Emissions [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Nitrosamines
Maasvlakte pilot PCC (da Silva et al., 2013a, 2013b)	2013	0.005 - 0.047	NDELA, NDMA and NMOR (aerosols: major contributor)
NPL monitoring, Tata pilot PCC [NPL internal report]	2023	0.040 - 0.080	NDMA, NDPA, NMOR
Loy Yang Pilot Plant (Azzi et al., 2014)	2014	0.4	NMOR (after wash water)
Gassnova (OCTAVIUS Session 1) (SEPA, 2015)	2014	< 0.003	NDMA, NDEA
Reported PCC stack emissions (SEPA, 2015)	2014	0.1 - 5	NDEA, NDMA, NMOR
Reported PCC stack emissions (SEPA, 2015)	2015	5*	Nitrosamines (TONO max.) *
Mongstad Test Centre (Berglen et al., 2010)	2010	5 - 9.9	Calculated worst case scenario. Nitrosamine as NDMA.
Ferrybridge, CCPilot100+ (Fitzgerald et al., 2014, SEPA, 2015)	2014	20*	TONO (max.) *
		11	NDiNA
		3.1	NDIBA
		1.8	NDELA
		0.5	NDBA
		0.2	NDMA

Notes: * Total nitrosamines (TONO) should be expressed as molar concentrations (e.g. mol/m^3), here the molecular mass of NDMA was used by these authors to express this value as a mass concentration (in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). The limitations to this practice will be discussed in Section 2.4.

the addition of a third impinger to the sampling train to improve the method. Similarly, Järvinen and collaborators states that the absorption efficiency should be determined for any sampling method to be used (Järvinen et al., 2012). Finally, Azzi and collaborators mentioned that this approach is compatible with volatile and semi-volatile nitrosamines like NMOR, although they also discuss the limitations in recovery efficiency for less volatile species (Azzi et al., 2014).

Table 2 summarises findings from the literature on nitrosamine measurements in post-combustion carbon capture (PCC) plants emissions, specifically those employing comparable wet chemical manual sampling techniques. In all reviewed studies, sampling was conducted using 2 to 4 impingers. Notably, each study either explicitly assumed or

Table 3
Some proposed nitrosamine limits reference values.

Institution / Company	Units [$\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$]	Limit
FORCE Technology (Andersen, 2025)	0.1	NDMA Air quality Emission Limit
SEPA review (SEPA, 2015)	0.01	Some suggested nitrosamine EALs
Norwegian Institute of Public Health (Låg et al. 2011; SEPA, 2015)	0.0003	EAL for total nitrosamines and nitramines (expressed as NDMA), also used as emission limit (as for permits)
USEPA (Manzoor, 2015)	0.00002	Nitrosamine Safety Limit via inhalation

Note: EALs stands for Environmental Assessment Levels.

implicitly treated the sampling recovery as 100 %, with no indication of correction factors or recovery losses being applied or discussed.

As demonstrated in the validation exercise presented in Section 4.1 (see Fig. 5), the recovery rates for nitrosamines with higher volatilities — namely NDMA, NMEA, NDEA, NDPA, and NPIP — were consistently 100 %. In contrast, species with lower volatilities, such as NDBA, NPYR, and NMOR, exhibited recovery rates of approximately 80 %. As an example, Table 2 reports emission values for several nitrosamines, including NDELA and NDINA, which has significantly lower vapour pressures (see Table 5). NDELA is typically measured using specialised sorbents (not water), such as glass fibre filters impregnated with KOH, as recommended by the IFA 8183 method for air quality monitoring. Furthermore, there are not available solubility values for some of the nitrosamines found in PCC plants (Table 5). However, in some cases these can be inferred. For instance, based on its chemical structure, which includes two bulky, branched alkyl chains, NDINA is likely to be hydrophobic and thus poorly soluble in water. This inference aligns with general findings from solubility studies on similar compounds (Avdeef et al., 2012; Singh et al., 2018; Hermans et al., 2023). It remains uncertain whether the liquid (water) impinger method is sufficiently effective for sampling species within the low volatility and/or low solubility ranges. In the case of nitrosamines exhibiting low recovery rates, substantial underestimations may occur, or their presence may go undetected altogether if the method's overall limit of detection (LoD) is not adequately low. That is why further studies including nitrosamine species featuring low solubility and/or low volatility are still required.

There are some works reporting concentration of nitrosamines only within the sample solution or within the solvent solution (CO_2 scrubber), these are also not mentioned here since the focus is on the atmospheric emissions.

On the other hand, within the available literature there are only a few references proposing values for nitrosamine limits. Table 3 summarise the most relevant ones as a guidance.

The effective manual monitoring limit of detection (e.g. in units of $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) results from the sampling recovery (% or fraction) and the detection limit of the used analytical method to measure the samples (e.g. for aqueous solutions in units of $\mu\text{g}/\text{L}$). Regardless of the applied limits it is important to optimise and assess the recovery of the manual sampling beforehand. Any manual stack emission monitoring method should meet a minimum list of performance requirements, with the detection limit being one of the most important.

2.3. Relevant physical and chemical properties of nitrosamines, potentially impacting the method

Volatility is one of the most important parameters related to nitrosamine atmospheric emissions. Possibly that is why most of the studies on nitrosamine PCC emissions have been focused precisely on the most volatile species. In fact, most of the volatile species listed in Table 1 have been measured in PCC emissions, from NDMA down to MNPZ, covering

a vapour pressure range from 0.4 to 0.002 kPa. Since these compounds are generally soluble, they can be transported in both gas (volatilised) and liquid phase (droplets and particles) (Maxime et al., 2024).

Due to the higher boiling points of volatile nitrosamines as compared to typical PCC stack temperatures, fine droplets of liquid with amines and nitrosamines may also be entrained within the exhaust gas. The formation of fine droplets is enhanced by foaming, which is known to be produced by most amine solutions. Therefore, regarding the atmospheric emissions, potentially nitrosamines will be found as fine liquid droplets, partially dissolved in the water liquid phase (water droplets), and in part behaving like gases in vapour form. In this intricate situation, each nitrosamine will have a different fractionation amongst these transporting vectors, since they have a wide range of water solubilities, although most of them are soluble. The same three transporting vectors apply as well to amines, nitramines and other degradation products, since all these species have overlapping ranges of the physical-chemical parameters driving these processes.

It is worth noting that the volatility of at least the six species at the bottom in Table 1 (or Table 5) do not account for their presence in the PCC flue gas emissions. However, NDELA (da Silva et al., 2013a, 2013b; Wang and Mitch, 2015; Morken et al., 2014; SEPA, 2015) and NDINA (SEPA, 2015) have been measured in PCC emissions, while NDELA and DNPZ have been measured in wash-water (Dai et al., 2012), meaning that the mentioned species can be transported within the flue gas. For that reason, it is most likely that these species were primarily transported by water droplets or particles. Therefore, the presence of liquid (vapourised water, ammonia or HCl) or solid (soot, H_2SO_4 , or salts) particles in the flue gases must be considered. In fact, many authors have verified that amine emissions scale up with the mist formation (Kolderup et al., 2012; Knudsen et al., 2013; Khakharia et al., 2016), and more recently it has been shown that amine emissions scale proportionally to the mist's particle number concentration (Lombardo et al., 2017; Dhanraj and Biswas, 2020; Yi et al., 2021 and references therein). This is also likely to be the case for nitrosamines and other pollutants, reinforcing the need of isokinetic sampling.

Further indirect evidence for the potential atmospheric emissions of nitrosamines with low volatilities is the fact that other low volatility amine degradation products have been shown to be transported by the vapour phase in PCC (Vevelstad et al., 2017). Vevelstad and collaborators have obtained measurements of several amines in the lean solvent and in the condensates found in the used plant vapour trapping system, among other compartments not mentioned here. Few of these compounds were found in both compartments mentioned, allowing us to compare these quantities. This is shown in Fig. 1, where it can be seen there are two radically different trends for the most volatile and the less volatile compounds. Data correspond to the fifth week of continuous operation using MEA as solvent.

Consistently the only species measured in high concentration (above 100 mg/L) in the lean solvent but found to be scarce in the condensate (below 0.01 mg/L) are those having low volatility (vapour pressure < 0.5 kPa). On the other hand, the volatile compounds can be found in both compartment with a difference lower than a factor 10. This is shown in Fig. 1 (right), where the log of the concentration ratios are close to zero (ratios constrained between 10^{-1} and 10^1). All these compounds are amines, which cover a wide range of volatilities, Table 4 summaries the list of measured amines along with their vapour pressures. This fact demonstrate that these molecules are being transported within the exhaust flow, regardless the value of their vapour pressure value. It is worth noting that this range of vapour pressures overlaps the range corresponding to the nitrosamines of interest in PCC emissions.

The potential nitrosamine emissions are also related to their thermal stability in the PCC process, since during usual PCC plant operating conditions (e.g., max. 120 °C) the temperatures are such that the nitrosamines remain stable and thermal decomposition of these compounds is not deemed as significant (Fine et al., 2014).

Regarding the nitrosamine's water solubility, the found values

Fig. 1. Concentration of amines measured in lean solvent and condensate (left), and concentration ratio (condensate / lean solvent) vs vapour pressure of each species (right).

Table 4
Amines measured by [Vedelstad et al. \(2017\)](#), and its vapour pressures (VP).

Compound	CAS	VP [kPa]	Compound	CAS	VP [kPa]
MMA	74-89-5	353	HEA	142-26-7	0.37
DMA	124-40-3	203	OZD	497-25-6	0.067
EA	75-04-7	140	HEF	693-06-1	$8.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$
NMEA	624-78-2	65	HEI	1615-14-1	$4.9 \cdot 10^{-5}$
3-Mpy	108-99-6	5.9	HEGly	5835-28-9	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$
Pyrazine	290-37-9	1.89	HEPO	23,936-04-1	$1.3 \cdot 10^{-7}$
2-Methylpyrazine	109-08-0	1.29	MEA urea	15,438-70-7	$6.4 \cdot 10^{-8}$
DM-Pyrazine	123-32-0	0.52	-	-	-

exhibit a large variability. For a variety of these nitrosamines some references claim they are water insoluble species, while other sources indicate solubility values (sometimes low values). [Table 5](#) reports the whole reported range, specifying just the extreme values.

Most of the nitrosamines are readily soluble in water, therefore the water droplets in the exhaust will likely contain dissolved

concentrations of nitrosamines, as commented above. However, in the case of insoluble nitrosamines the flow dynamics do not rely on water transportation, causing a differentiation in the exhaust component's flue patterns for nitrosamines having different volatilities. This will impact the manual wet sampling, since the higher solubility, the more efficient the impingers will be, enhancing the recovery of the nitrosamines

Table 5
Nitrosamines: relevant properties.

Compound	Vapour pressure, kPa	Boiling point, °C	Melting point, °C	Physical state	Water solubility (g/L)	Other solubilities
NDMA	0.40	152	-25 to 50	Liquid	100 to 1000	alcohols, ether, ethyl ether, chloroform. Lipids.
NMEA	0.34	154	-25, <27	Liquid	Not miscible or difficult to mix. or 300	Chloroform (sparingly), ethyl acetate & methanol (slight)
NDEA	0.10	179	<25	Oil	100 to 106	Organic solvents, lipids
NDiPA	0.035	195	48	Solid	13	Methanol, ethanol, benzene
NDPA	0.030	206	-12 to 6.6	Liquid	Not miscible or difficult to mix. or 0.01 to 10	Alcohol; ether; organic; lipids
NMOx	0.016	217, 227	NAI	NAI	NAI	NAI
NPIP	0.012	225	7 to 48	Liquid	10 to 77	Organic solvents and lipids, HCl
NDBA	0.006	237	<25	Liquid	1.27 to 120	Organic solvents and vegetable oils
NDIBA	0.0057	236, 238	-98	Oil	0.6 to 3	NAI
NPYR	0.0050	214	29	Liquid	53 to 1000	Organic solvents and lipids. Methanol (slightly)
NMOR	0.0048	224	29	Liquid	100	Organic solvents
MNPZ	0.0020	265	54	Oil, semi-solid, hygroscopic	54 to 747	Chloroform, Ethyl Acetate (slight)
EHEN	0.00012	273	35	Liquid	Insoluble, 25, 382	Methanol, chloroform (slight)
NMELA	0.00008	277	NAI	Oil	NAI	Methanol, chloroform (slight)
NDELA	0.00007	376	57, 108	Very viscous liquid	100 to 1000	Polar organic solvents
DNPZ	0.000025	263, 299, 406	103, 156, 210	Solid (hygroscopic)	14	Chloroform DMSO, Methanol (Slightly)
NHEGly	$6 \cdot 10^{-7}$	352, 449	80, 116	Solid	1000	DMSO
NDINA	Low - NAI	385	NAI	Oil	NAI	Chloroform and ethyl acetate (slightly)

Notes: NAI stands for no available information. Again, the eight specific nitrosamines used in the experimental validation of the manual monitoring method presented in this work are highlighted in bold letters. In some cases, several parameter values were found.

passing through within the sampling flow.

Water-wash is an important feature of all amine scrubbing technologies, which is the first line of defence against emissions of volatile compounds (as ammonia and amine degradation products) and aerosols, also condensing water from the flue gas contributing to maintain the water balance of the solvent loop (Rochelle, 2024). However, it is necessary to verify the efficacy of the water-wash and whether they meet the permitted emissions levels. This is particularly important due to the different emissions levels caused by the solvent conditions and its continuous degradation, which accumulate in the solvent increasing amounts of undesirable breakdown products. In fact, pilot plant studies have found nitrosamine concentrations in wash-water samples that exceed the USEPA and the Norwegian Environment Agency regulatory limits (Safaei and Young, 2024). This implies that even a fraction of these compounds breaking through the water-wash system could suppose concerning emissions, which would involve both solvent amines and volatile degradation compounds with the CO₂-cleaned exhaust gas, particularly in cases where the PCC plant is not equipped with rigid emission mitigation technologies (Maxime et al., 2024). Also, more measurements of amine and nitrosamine emissions at different sites would be helpful to further quantify the plants performance (Rochelle, 2024). For that reasons, standard monitoring methods to quantify those emissions are still required even in the best cases.

To preserve the chemical stability of the nitrosamines during the sampling, sample storage and transport, it is necessary to select suitable materials preventing any undesired effect. N-nitroso compounds may react in aqueous solutions with nucleophilic agents; it is needed to avoid reaction with oxidizing agents. NDMA reacts with natural and nitrile rubbers, neoprene, PVA, PVC, Viton, and other organics, while NDPA is stable at 20–24 °C for more than 14 days in neutral or alkaline solutions (in dark), but less stable in acidic solutions. Finally, NPYR reacts with oxidizing agents such as perchlorates, peroxides, permanganates, chlorates, nitrates, chlorine, bromine and fluorine. This nitrosamine is potentially incompatible with cellulose-based and expanded polymeric absorbents and reacts vigorously with reducing agents (Li, Na, Al). For the above reasons, during the sampling only stainless steel and borosilicate glassware will be used, and brown borosilicate will be used for sample storage.

Table 5 includes the relevant parameters for the nitrosamines listed in Table 1. The focus here are the parameters potentially impacting the sampling process. It is worth commenting that all the PCC researched nitrosamines (20 in total) are less volatile than water, and none will be above its corresponding boiling point under standard PCC operation conditions (which is generally lower than 120 °C).

Also, they are sensitive to light, specially to ultraviolet radiation, being necessary to store the samples in a dark glass or other suitable light resistant container which is securely sealed. When the photolysis occurs, the nitrosamines generally degrade to amines and NO_x. For example, the main products of NDMA and NDELA include methylamine, dimethylamine, nitrite, nitrate (Lee and Wexler, 2013).

Nitrites are commonly formed by several processes, with the most important the nitrification of ammonia. Significant amounts of this compound are usually detected in the PCC exhausts, evidencing the potential formation of nitrosamines. Also, nitrosamines can rapidly be formed at basic pH because the nitrogen oxides are direct nitrosating agents and do not require an acid medium to be transformed into agents for nitrosation (Perera, 2006). To prevent further nitrosamine formation during sampling and storage stages, the effect of nitrites on secondary amines should be considered, particularly when acidic solutions are used.

Sulfamic acid was originally used in nitrite estimation methods (Rider and Mellon, 1946). Since then, it has also been used as a pre-treatment to remove nitrite, for instance, in isotopic analysis (Wu et al., 1997) and multi-isotope (N and O) analysis of nitrate (Granger and Sigman, 2009). More recently, sulfamic acid has become the most common means of preventing undesirable nitrosamine formation during

sampling and storage of PCC stack samples, particularly due to the presence of amine species that can potentially undergo nitrosation and form new nitrosamines within the samples if this precautionary measure is ignored. Also, other nitrosation inhibitors have been described in the literature, as ascorbic acid, tocopherol (Perera, 2006), or sodium hydroxide (Huang et al., 2013).

High levels of amines, aldehydes, and nitrite in samples from the exhaust of PCC presented a risk for the artefactual formation of N-nitrosamines during sample storage or analysis. The application of a 30-fold molar excess of sulfamic acid to nitrite at pH 2 destroys nitrite with no significant risk of artefactual nitrosation of amines (Dai et al., 2012). Then, it necessary to estimate the nitrite content in the samples (to adjust the amount of sulfamic acid) or using the sulfamic acid as a chemical reagent in excess. Some direct applications to nitrosamines atmospheric emissions from CO₂ capture plants have been done using cold impingers filled with 0.1 M sulfamic acid in water, obtaining good results (Fraboulet et al., 2016). This procedure is implemented in the present work.

In all the validation tests Thermo-Sorb-N (Ellutia, Cambridgeshire, England, UK) cartridges were used at the end of each impinger series, in order to collect the possible nitrosamine breakthrough, and if this is the case allowing evaluation of the extent of such a breakthrough under the test conditions. Also, such cartridges play a role in terms of our health & safety and environmental standards.

Finally, it is clear that the diversity of the nitrosamines and their specific behaviours should be considered during the sampling and monitoring. In this context, it is important to note that there is a continuous update on the proposed amines and cocktails to be used in PCC (Wang and Song, 2020; Brakstad et al., 2023). These new solvents and the possible impact of the diverse set of breakthrough products, particularly the nitrosamines, should be addressed in the near future.

2.4. Limitations on the application of Toxic Equivalents for nitrosamines

The nitrosamines have a large variety of molecular structures and properties. They belong to the named group of compounds (nitrosamines) due to the presence of the nitroso functional group (N–N=O) in otherwise completely different organic compounds. In fact, the wide range of values for all the relevant physical and chemical parameters is related to their susceptibility to undergo into specific chemical reactions, or driving their formation, stability, transport and thermodynamical behaviour. For instance, the nitrosamine's volatility (vapour pressure) covers 7 orders of magnitude, their solubility is variable among the different species, they include linear compounds and ring type species, and their molecular masses ranges from 74 to 299 g/mol.

The selection of any surrogate substance assumes that the selected species has similar physicochemical properties, toxicological effects or environmental fate properties as the whole group of compounds, but none of these assumptions holds in the case of the nitrosamines. For that reason, it is not possible to find a surrogate nitrosamine capable of representing the whole family of compounds.

The application of a Toxic Equivalent approach is only valid in cases where the target molecules are similar enough regarding their dynamic properties (transport, sampling recovery, etc.), as in the case of dioxins. However, in the case of nitrosamines the argument of "similarity" required to define a surrogate cannot be accomplished, therefore this approach is unrealistic, since any selected species is not representative of the whole group of nitrosamines found in PCC. For that reason, this simplified approach should not be used in this instance.

On the other hand, figures as the EAL proposed by the Norwegian Institute of Public Health (0.3ng/m³) for total nitrosamines expressed as NDMA (Svendensen et al., 2023), cannot be adopted as a fully derived and established benchmark due to the differences in the way that different countries assess carcinogenicity (SEPA, 2015).

Finally, sampling and measuring all the different nitrosamines found in PCC (over 20 species) is a major challenge, which probably will not be

feasible using one single sampling and one single analytical method. For that reason, the present work is focused only on volatile nitrosamines.

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Tracing solutions and sample storage conditions

The reference standard material used for the laboratory test is the EPA 8270/Appendix IX Nitrosamines Mix. This consists of a set of nine nitrosamines mixed at the same concentration in a methanol matrix. In Table 6 the concentration of each nitrosamine in this reference standard is specified, the data is provided by the manufacturer.

NDPhA (N-Nitroso-Diphenylamine, CAS 86-30-6) was present in the standard and the used solution, however, it was not used since the employed analytical method was not applicable to this species.

No statistical correlation exists between the certified concentrations and their corresponding uncertainties. However, a clear correlation can be seen between the declared uncertainties and the nitrosamines' vapour pressure. Fig. 2 shows this linear correlation, which means that the more volatile the species, the more variable the concentration, even for manufacturing laboratories. This unexpected relationship suggests that vapour pressure is a key parameter for the behaviour of these compounds.

The tracing solution was diluted with deionised water to produce the different tracing aliquots, with the desired concentrations, to be used during the method validation.

Literature reports a wide list of sample storage times and temperature values. Some sources suggest storage at room temperature; however, other references strongly suggest that the storage temperature must be as low as $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for many of the nitrosamines of interest. A preliminary test series on sample storage times and temperature were carried out in the present work to define the more convenient conditions. The test was performed using purpose made nitrosamine traced synthetic samples.

Two sample batches (6 samples each) were produced using the above-described reference standard. The procedure consisted of preparing carefully weighed dilutions in 0.1 M sulfamic acid. The final dilutions contained approximately $30\text{ }\mu\text{g/L}$ per nitrosamine species. Each batch of six samples was separated in two groups, 3 samples (replicas) were stored and transported at room temperature, while the other 3 samples were refrigerated ($4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) during storage and delivery (transported using ice packs). Temperature was record for all the samples during the storage and transport to the laboratory (temperature data loggers). The first batch was sent to the laboratory just after it was produced, and the second one was stored for one week before being sent to the laboratory for analysis. The samples were measured by Gas Chromatography (GC) coupled to a Thermal Energy Analyser (TEA).

Thermal Energy Analysis (TEA) was selected due to its sensitive and selective detection capability for analysing nitrosamines. When combined with Gas Chromatography (GC -TEA), it can be used to detect different nitrosamine species in each sample. TEA works by pyrolyzing

Fig. 2. Certified nitrosamines' uncertainties and vapour pressures.

the sample to break the N—N bond within the nitrosamine molecule and releasing nitric oxide (NO). The NO is then reacted with ozone to form excited nitrogen dioxide NO_2^* , which emits light at a specific wavelength that is detected and quantified. Furthermore, sulfamic acid is non-volatile and does not interfere with GC-TEA measurements. On the other hand, if an amine co-elutes with a nitrosamine, it might not be detected by TEA (since it doesn't produce NO). This is a convenient way to reduce interferences from amines, since the PCC collected samples are likely to contain the amine(s) used as scrubber and several other amine species resulting from degradation. However, in case of simultaneous co-elution of amines it could affect the peak shape or baseline, complicating the quantification. Also, if the co-eluted amine's concentration is high enough it could cause matrix effects, potentially altering the retention time or thermal decomposition efficiency of nitrosamines, especially in complex mixtures. Since in actual stack samples the used solvent amine (or cocktail) is likely to be the one emitted in larger concentrations, it is advisable to perform cross interference tests, at least with the scrubber amine(s), to assess the extent of these potential issues.

It is worth noting that the combination of the described sampling and analytical method is suitable for volatile nitrosamines. Further research should be devoted to proposing and assess methods for PCC nitrosamines with lower volatility, as EHEN, NMELA, NDELA, DNPZ, NHEGLy and NDiNA. For instance, NDELA is usually captured and measured by a different method (IFA 8183), using glass fibre filters impregnated in KOH (IFA, 2000). However, this method was optimised for air analysis, being its lower sampling rate and allowed humidity ranges the main limitation to be adapted to stack sampling methods.

All the samples show a good preservation of the proportion between the eight measured nitrosamines, showing that no differential fractionation among the species is occurring within the individual samples. Each sample has a well-defined average concentration, within one standard deviation $< 10\%$ for the eight different nitrosamines.

It is worth mentioning that the uncertainty declared by the analytical laboratory is $\pm 10\%$ of the reported nitrosamine values. However, in the case of samples preserved at room temperature, the replicas have concentration values largely dispersed ($\pm 40\%$ for different replicas). This dispersion is related to each sample as a whole rather than to individual nitrosamines behaviour. This happens in both cases, immediate and delayed samples. In fact, the 3 replicas can't be averaged since they have statistically different values (either significantly above or below the nominal concentration). Therefore, this storage temperature cannot be used.

In contrast, in the case of refrigerated samples the measurements have a lower dispersion. The standard deviation of individual samples is $8\text{--}10\%$ for immediate, and 8% for delayed replicas, which are comparable to the 3 replica's dispersion (9% for both groups). The storage time seems to be not so significant within the mentioned standard deviation, although a slight diminution of the concentration was observed in the one-week delayed samples as compared with the immediately

Table 6

Nitrosamines' reference standard material concentrations and uncertainties.

Nitrosamine	Certified concentration	Certified uncertainty
-	$\mu\text{g/mL}$	$\mu\text{g/mL}$
NDMA	2004	65
NMEA	2001	42
NDEA	2001	29
NPIP	2000	13
NDPA	2001	13
NDBA	2004	15
NPYR	2018	15
NMOR	1999	15
NDPhA	1997	15

measured (Fig. A1, Annex). So, the refrigeration method was used in all the tests.

A last test with synthetic liquid samples was conducted to investigate the potential effect of longer storage times. A synthetic sample was made with 10 µg/mL per nitrosamine species using the same reference standard. The storage time of this solution was one month, keeping the sample bottle refrigerated (4 °C) at all times. In this case, all the nitrosamines were measured with lower and more dispersed values, being this reduction more evident in the case of nitrosamines with higher volatility (Fig. A1, Annex). In summary, an ageing effect was observed after one month, so we suggest analysing the samples within one week if possible.

3.2. Experimental set up – NPL sampling performance assessment test rig

Typical PCC flue gas conditions were simulated in a scaled down experimental bench, where all the gas flows and conditions were carefully controlled (Fig. 3). A series of three impingers were used to capture the target analytes after passing them through the experimental system, I1 being the first one and I3 the last. All the impingers were filled with approximately 200 mL of an aqueous solution of 0.1 M sulfamic acid. A Thermo-Sorb cartridge was placed at the back end of the capture system in order to capture any possible breakthrough of nitrosamines. After each test the 3 impingers and the probe were rinsed with water (samples labelled as PW – probe wash) to collect any nitrosamines deposited on the glassware surfaces. Due to the oily and sticky nature of some nitrosamines the full efficiency of the wash can't be guaranteed.

In the case of Thermo-Sorb-N cartridges, they have been validated, and storage times and conditions have been suggested (Rounbehler et al., 1980), so we used the manufacturer recommendations (although they are originally designed for air-borne nitrosamines). Thermo-Sorb-N cartridges use an inhibitor to prevent degradation during sampling and storage.

Besides the equipment described in the schematic, there were used also other instruments to heat the test probe, to measure the total flow rate and the total volume of gas passing through the system while emulating an isokinetic sampling. These instruments are the same that will be used on field works with the actual PCC stacks.

3.3. Sampling and nitrosamine analysis validation test

All the used gas cylinders correspond to certified gases. The synthetic PCC gas stream composition included air, water vapour, NO_x (72 ppm of NO and 7 ppm of NO₂), CO (21 ppm) and SO₂ (5.7 ppm), which are

usually encountered in PCC flue gases. Here, ppm refers micro mol of the mentioned substance by mol of the mixture (µmol/mol).

The nitrosamines were injected with a precision syringe set at an approximate range of 0.05 mL per minute, to deliver 3 mL of solution along the test duration (typically one hour). The solution was a dilution of the same reference standard used in the previous tests (EPA 8270). A total of fifteen tests, T1 to T15, were performed at the same temperature (80 °C) and pressure (atmospheric), and using the same blend of 8 nitrosamines, as described in the previous tests with the “synthetic” samples. The test plan is summarised below.

- T1 blank (water injection, day 1)
- T2-T3 nitrosamine injection (day 2)
- T4 blank (water injection, day 3)
- T5 nitrosamine injection (day 4)
- T6 nitrosamine injection (day 5)
- T7 blank (water injection, day 5)
- T8 nitrosamine injection (day 5)
- T9 blank (water injection, day 9)
- T10 -T14 nitrosamine injection (day 10)
- T15 nitrosamine injection (day 12)

Each test lasted for one hour, in which a nitrosamine mass of 6 to 7.4 micro grams (per species) was injected into the test bench, this represented a concentration of approximately 6.8 µg/m³ of each nitrosamine, bubbled through the impingers at a constant rate of 15.5 L/min. These conditions are approximately equivalent to six-hour sampling with an emitted concentration of 1 µg/m³ (per species). The repeatability of the test series performed in fixed conditions was the focus during this validation phase. All the experiments were then performed to allow direct comparability of the results, using the same gas matrix, almost identical gas conditions and practically the same amount of nitrosamines injected. Temperature of the probe and the sampling line was 80 °C, and it was maintained below the dew point to allow the presence of water vapour droplets. The pressure was slightly above the atmospheric pressure.

During the tests, the main gas stream (15.5 L/min) was divided in two using a T connector and a valve. A reduced stream (about 10 % of the total flow) was passed through the Thermo-Sorb cartridges, which have an operational flow rate range of 0.2–4 L/min. In order to avoid the potential dispersion of the nitrosamines in the surrounding environment, the larger fraction of the stream was forced to pass through 2 serial-connected activated carbon filters (1,5 litres of volume each), to prevent any pollutant breaking through the system.

All the samples were refrigerated immediately after sampling.

Fig. 3. Schematic of the test bench for the nitrosamine liquid sampling test.

During transport to the laboratory, the samples were kept cold by storing them with ice packs inside thermally insulated boxes (expanded polystyrene). Upon arrival the sample conditions were checked and verified by means of temperature loggers. Then, the samples were analysed by Gas Chromatography coupled to a Thermo-Energy Analyser (GC-TEA) using the IFA 7748/3 IV/03 method for volatile nitrosamines, which uses a specific chromatographic column (often a DB-624). The blank test (T1) registered values below the corresponding method detection limit, equivalent to $\approx 0.05 \mu\text{g}$ of each nitrosamine for the liquid samples and equal to 4 ng within the Thermo-Sorb cartridges.

The recovery of each one of the 3 impingers and the total impinger recovery is analysed. Two different criteria were applied to assess the wet sampling method, and the results are discussed considering individual nitrosamine physic-chemical properties. Then, the analysis of the missing fractions of nitrosamines is discussed.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Sampling recovery using two different criteria

Box and whisker plots in Fig. 4 illustrate the results obtained in all the tests where nitrosamines were injected into the test system. The first impinger captured the largest amounts of nitrosamines, although it also showed the largest variability. As expected, it was followed by the second impinger, whose captured an also sizeable amounts of nitrosamines. However, each individual nitrosamine behaves in a different manner.

All the measurements were reported originally as concentrations, μg of each nitrosamine per litre of solution per each one of the eight measured nitrosamines (Tables A1-A5). However, the graphs in Fig. 4 are presented as mass percentage, where 100 % represents the total amount of nitrosamines injected during each test ($n = 11$ tests injecting nitrosamines).

As expected, for all the studied species systematically the amount captured in the first impinger is the largest one, the second impinger captured an intermediate value and the last impinger captured the lower amount of the analyte. However, there is no correlation between the nitrosamine fractions captured by the individual impingers, showing different individual behaviours instead a general trend.

The first criterium to assess the total impinger recovery is shown in Fig. 5, where the sum of the 3 impingers is indicating the recovery (yield) of the whole liquid sampling system.

The three nitrosamines with lower volatility are partially captured within the liquid sampling system, some 75 to 80 % (in average), and exhibit the largest variability. The missing 25 to 20 % will be discussed below. The 5 most volatile nitrosamines are well over 100 % showing

the suitability of the method for volatile nitrosamines. However, if we add the nitrosamines recovered during the probe wash (PW) and the ones captured by the dry cartridges, a graph similar to Fig. 5 will be obtained but with a sampling recovery near 110 % instead (not shown). This systematic positive bias could be due to a systematic lack of accuracy of the injection system. However, during the calibration and testing the used injection system reported high accuracy and precision (results always within 0.5 % using one-hour tests). Another potential cause could be a systematic bias in the weighting of the used aliquots of the nitrosamines reference material, but they were carefully prepared in two different batches showing practically the same results.

Also, it is worth discussing the possibility of an overall systematic analytical overestimation of the sample's nitrosamine content measured in the laboratory due to a potential cross-contamination. The samples contain only gases partially dissolved (from the simulated post capture flue gas described in Section 3.3), the nitrosamines mentioned in Table 6, sulfamic acid, and no added amines. In principle, the NO in the sample may be directly detected by the TEA system, while NO₂ can be converted to NO during injection, both potentially contributing to the background signal or complicating the nitrosamines quantification. In the case of NO₂, it is a highly volatile and reactive compound, and molecules like this often elute near the dead time or decompose, making impractical to estimate a retention index or a retention time on standard GC columns (Onuska and Karasek, 1984). On the other hand, the separation in the GC column seems to be enough to avoid measuring the nitric oxide effect while measuring the nitrosamines, since NO is a gas with very short retention times, typically eluting well before nitrosamines. This inorganic and highly volatile compound is non-retained under typical GC conditions used for organic VOCs. Table A6 (Annex) shows typical retention times for some nitrosamines and NO in chromatographic columns. It can be seen that NDMA (the most volatile nitrosamine) elutes in about 4 min, while the nitric oxide elutes before 0.33 min, providing a time resolution capable to discern between their signals. Other less volatile and heavier nitrosamines have even larger retention times, reducing the probability of their measurements being affected by the presence of nitric oxide. Furthermore, nitric oxide can be separated by GC even from VOCs with higher volatility than that of nitrosamines. For instance, it has been shown that NO is separated from an ethylene matrix (mass 28 g/mol, BP $-104 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, VP 7.103 kPa) using a capillary porous layer open tubular column (PLOT) (PAC, 2016). It is worth noting that the comparison shown in Table A6 (Annex) is the worst case scenario, since the reported retention times for nitrosamines correspond to a wall coated open tubular column (WCOT) like the DB-624, while for NO this corresponds to a porous polymer columns, which are packed capillary columns having longer retention times than

Fig. 4. Box plots of the recoveries for impingers 1, 2 and 3 (connected in series), $n = 11$.

Fig. 5. Total nitrosamine's sampling yield [%]. 3 impingers combined, $n = 11$.

WCOT columns under comparable conditions. For WCOT columns nitric oxide retention times are not reported (as far as we know), so a direct comparison was not possible. For the above-mentioned reasons, it is unlikely that the origin of the observed overestimation could be related to cross-contamination impacting the GC-TEA measurements.

Finally, regarding the analytical calibration and generalities of the method, they were performed as indicated in the IFA 7748/3 IV/03 method for volatile nitrosamines.

Although we are still investigating on the possible sources of this overestimation, fortunately, the observed overall positive bias is not impacting the general results and the analysis presented here.

The second criterium to assess the impinger efficiency is applying the absorber efficiency check, a general practice used in stack monitoring for manual extractive techniques. The absorber efficiency check is passed if $<5\%$ of the measured pollutant is left on the last impinger of the sample train, as described in the *MCERTS performance standard for manual stack emission monitoring organisations* (Environment Agency, 2024). In this case, Fig. 6 (left) and Table 7 illustrate the amounts of nitrosamines captured by the 3rd impinger, taking as 100 % the total amount of nitrosamines collected in the three impingers and the probe water (which is the available data in stack monitoring).

All the relevant data (measured values above the detection limits) are shown in the tables within the Annex.

NDPA and NDBA have considerable breakthrough into the last impinger, therefore failing the absorber efficiency check. NDEA amounts in the 3rd impinger lays in the border, making difficult to assess whether it passed the criteria ($\leq 5\%$). The other 5 nitrosamines have $<5\%$ breakthrough into the last impinger (on average) and using this

Table 7
Nitrosamines collected in the last impinger.

Nitrosamine	3rd impinger yield
NDMA	$2.3 \pm 1.2\%$
NMEA	$2.9 \pm 1.6\%$
NDEA	$5.3 \pm 3.2\%$
NDPA	$11 \pm 7\%$
NPIP	$1.5 \pm 1.0\%$
NDBA	$22 \pm 12\%$
NPYR	$0.2 \pm 0.6\%$
NMOR	$0.2 \pm 0.7\%$

second criterion could be considered well captured using this sampling criterium. This be seen in Table 7, where the values in red correspond to failures of the absorber efficiency check. One of the advantages of this criterium is that it doesn't require a tracing test to determine whether the capture was efficient or not. For this reason, it is generally used in real-life situations based solely on measured results.

Ring structured nitrosamines are the only species practically non collected in the 3rd impinger (the last impinger) regardless of their volatility, while linear nitrosamines having the lowest volatility (NDPA and NDBA) are the ones exhibiting higher values in this last impinger.

The average amount of nitrosamines breaking through the first two impingers and being captured by the last impinger (the 3rd one) correlates with the volatility (Fig. 6 right). The lower the volatility the larger the nitrosamine fraction passing through and being captured by the third impinger. This relationship holds only for linear type nitrosamines, while ring type nitrosamines are barely captured in the last

Fig. 6. Values of third impinger recoveries ($n = 11$) and their relationship with volatility.

impinger. This time, the last impinger recovery was calculated considering the total amount of injected nitrosamines as 100 % (which is more realistic).

Unfortunately, no relationship can be inferred between these values and the numerical values of the nitrosamine's water solubilities, due to the lack of reliable and accurate solubility data, as shown in Table 5.

In summary, using the first criterion we shown that the five most volatile nitrosamines are captured efficiently by the system, while the three less volatile nitrosamines were sampled with lower recoveries (Fig. 5). While using the second criterion only the less volatile linear nitrosamines failed the recovery test. The discrepancy between the two used criteria is explained in the next section.

4.2. Analysis of the missing nitrosamines

Ring type nitrosamines (NPYP, NPYR and NMOR), were seen to be partially trapped within the measurement system (test system and/or impinger walls) and then recovered during the washing procedure (PW). Also, significant amounts of linear nitrosamines with lower volatility (NDPA and NDBA) can partially pass through the impingers to the back cartridge. This can be seen in Fig. 7, where the probe wash solutions and dry cartridge nitrosamine mass (%) are represented as box and whisker plots.

The nitrosamines recovered within the probe wash (PW) are of the same type with the ones recovered in the blank tests after the nitrosamine's injection tests (insufficient PW efficiency). This shows that the species most attached to the surfaces during the test are always the same ones. This is illustrated in Fig. 8, where the percentage of nitrosamines recovered in the blank tests (average of 3 blanks) – from remaining contamination of previous tests – is represented against the amounts recovered by the probe wash (average of PW from 11 tests). The shown correlation shows that the species most attached to internal surfaces (including glassware, sampling lines and connections) are NPYR and NMOR, the less volatile nitrosamines.

The nitrosamines melting points are related to their viscosity, being oil type substances, they behave as more viscous and sticky substances the closer they are to their melting points. In the case of nitrosamines with lower volatility, this increases the risk of them becoming attached to the inner surfaces of the glassware used for sampling (impingers and lines).

Finally, the nitrosamines that breaks through the three impingers and pass to the dry backend cartridge are always linear nitrosamines, mainly the ones having low volatility. In fact, the amounts captured correlates with the volatility of each species (negative slope correlation with the log of the vapour pressure at 20 °C). Fig. 9 presents the box plot

Fig. 8. Nitrosamines in an after blank vs. the ones recovered with the probe wash (PW).

for the nitrosamine amounts found in the back end cartridges in the 11 tests (left) and also shows how these averaged quantities correlates with the vapour pressure values for linear type nitrosamines, as shown in Fig. 9 (right), where three of the cartridges were below the limit of detection.

However, again this correlation holds just for the linear nitrosamines and not for ring type ones (Fig. 9 right). These were systematically below the detection limit of 4 ng for the Thermo-Sorb samples, so they were either partially captured by the impingers and the reminding amounts were stuck within the system's walls and inner surfaces. This behaviour agrees with the nitrosamines found in the last impinger (Fig. 6), since the larger the nitrosamine fraction in the third impinger the greater the likelihood to trespass this last impinger and being captured by the ThermoSorb cartridge placed in the back end.

The behaviour of ring-type structures like NPYP, NPYR and NMOR (and probably others such as MNPZ, etc.) is different when compared to linear-structured nitrosamines. The ring type nitrosamines are better retained in the system. Their low volatility alone cannot explain this, since NDBA (linear type) and NPYR (ring type) have practically the same value of vapour pressure, but NDBA is well captured in the cartridges while the NPYR is not.

In general, nitrosamines contain a nitroso group ($-N=O$) and it is well known that these are molecules with a strong dipolar nature and exhibit mesomeric effects (Anselme, 1979; Yaghmaeiyan et al., 2023), being capable of engaging in dipole-dipole interactions and hydrogen bonding with polar surfaces, including silica-based materials or polymeric coatings. However, surface interaction and adsorption mechanism

Fig. 7. Nitrosamines recovered in PW and Thermo-Sorb cartridges, $n = 11$.

Fig. 9. Nitrosamines captured by Thermo-Sorbs and their relationship with volatility.

varies from the different nitrosamine species. Cyclic nitrosamines, such as NPYR, NPIP or NMOR, have rigid ring structures that enhance planarity and pi-electron density, increasing van der Waals and dipole interactions with polar surfaces. Also, the ring structure allows better surface contact geometry, promoting adsorption. Cyclic nitrosamines are likely to have higher dipole moments, and polar surface areas as compared to linear analogues, although no reported values of these properties have been found. These properties increase hydrogen bonding potential with silanol groups on glass or silica surfaces, and promote adsorption via polar interactions, especially in mildly acidic conditions.

Acid-catalysed nitrosation of some heterocyclic secondary amines and their 1-oxide derivatives is a reversible process. Seemingly, these nitrosamines readily undergo denitrosation (Kalatzis and Papadopoulos, 1981). Within the studied nitrosamines NPIP, NPYR and NMOR are heterocyclic structures, so they could undergo back-degradation to secondary amines, making difficult to assess their actual amounts during the sampling and storing processes. In principle, the denitrosation by inorganic acids is slow, but is faster in hot or anhydrous media (Scanlan and Tannenbaum, 1981). The slow rate of this process in aqueous media open the possibility to apply the wet sampling method using an impinger solutions, however this mechanism shouldn't be neglected. A fraction of the ring-type nitrosamines could undergo back-degradation, reducing their concentrations within the samples. This could help to explain the impinger recovery values for these species which were significantly lower when compared with other species of similar volatilities

The results of the nitrosamine test are representative only in the case of nitrosamines having a high or moderate volatility, but not necessarily for low volatile nitrosamines. Specific research on the applicability of the proposed method to less volatile nitrosamines is encouraged.

5. Conclusions

A test bench for nitrosamine's sampling test at laboratory scale was developed and tested, this can be used to carefully control all the relevant parameters to mimic the behaviour of an industrial PCC plant stack. The described system can simulate different flue gas compositions and a range of conditions, allowing further studies including the performance assessment of manual or continuous monitoring methods. This can be used for nitrosamines, amines or other target species.

The performance of the wet chemical impinger sampling method using 3 consecutive impingers and one back-end dry cartridge was tested for eight volatile nitrosamines, being NMOR the less volatile one (vapour pressure 0.0048 kPa). The present method could be extrapolated to MNPZ (0.0020 kPa), but the corresponding recovery should be assessed. We discourage the use of this method for species with lower volatility, as EHEN (0.00012 kPa) and the other nitrosamines listed in

Table 5 (unless proven otherwise).

The liquid sampling has a range of recoveries of between 70 – 110 % for individual nitrosamines, while the total recovery (impingers, probe waters and cartridges combined) shows analytical overestimation for the more volatile nitrosamines (repeatability exhibit a large variability).

It was shown that the impingers' efficiency depends on the volatility of the specific species, and the sampling process depends on the type of molecular structure. The ring type nitrosamines have lower recoveries as compared with linear ones with similar volatilities. Also, cross contamination was observed to be an important factor for the ring type nitrosamines, and a better probe/impinger cleaning method would be necessary. Surface conditions affect the impinger's efficiency for low volatile nitrosamines and is one of the important factors affecting the observed variability.

The validated liquid sampling method, together with analytical measurements, offers good results for the most volatile nitrosamines. As explained, two criteria were used to analyse the obtained results. The total recovery and the absorber efficiency check (5 %).

Using the total recovery criterium, five species can be regarded as well sampled, they are NDMA, NMEA, NDEA, NPIP and NDPA, while the other 3 nitrosamines (NDBA, NPYR and NMOR) are sampled in a lower proportion (75 to 80 %). On the other hand, using the absorber efficiency check, both some high and low volatile nitrosamines pass the test, while only 2 intermediate linear nitrosamines, NDBA and NDPA, do not pass this test, as they are significantly present in the last impinger.

The two applied criteria for evaluating the wet sampling efficiency gives differing results for intermediate and low volatile nitrosamines, this leads to the open question on the criterion that must be applied for the case of these complex chemicals. For NDMA, NMEA, NDEA and NPIP both criteria are passed, which allows us to assume that the most volatile nitrosamines can be monitored by this sampling method if an analytical method is provided. However, nitrosamines with lower volatilities fail either one or the other used the criterium. For that reason, it is advisable to introduce some modifications in the sampling to achieve a recovery close to 100 % for all the nitrosamines. The first proposed modification is using one additional impinger with the same 0.1 M sulfamic acid aqueous solution, in order to increase the total capture capacity of the impinger train. The second modification consists of reducing the inlet flue gas temperature before the impingers. It could be achieved by using a coil condenser as the one used for sampling dioxins. The reduction of the temperature will increase the solubility of the target analytes and reduce their volatility, increasing the overall capture capacity of the system. Finally, using a knockout impactor with a relatively large volume at the beginning of the impinger train would also enhance the efficacy of the sampling system (as proposed by Gangstad and Nenseter, 2014). The last proposals have been conceived considering the standard equipment and materials already available for any team dedicated to

stack emissions monitoring, so these changes do not constitute a significant added cost of the monitoring system. It would be advisable to conduct future validation tests on the suggested changes or on any other modification intended to improve the recovery of the semi-volatile nitrosamines.

The present study and the conclusions presented here can be applied to the studied nitrosamines, and they could be carefully extrapolated to other nitrosamines with similar volatilities and similar structures (linear or ring type). However, other PCC low volatile nitrosamines, as NDELA and EHEN, are expected to behave in a different manner, since they have vapour pressures one to two orders of magnitude below the less volatile species studied here (see Table 5). For that reason, further research focus on nitrosamines with lower volatility is highly encouraged.

The stack conditions during a PCC plant operation may be different to the ones used here, also those conditions can vary across time. It is advisable to undertake further research scoped to assess the validity of the proposed methods in a wider range of conditions.

Although the presented method for manual stack sampling was developed for nitrosamines potentially emitted from PCC, in principle, it could be adapted for amines within the same volatility range (0.002 to 0.4 kPa). Experimental studies are encouraged to validate this sampling method for amines, investigating the volatility range in which it could be applied to sample relevant amine species in PCC plants. Amines are basic compounds and include species that can volatilise during sampling. However, for manual stack amine sampling it has been suggested to add sulfuric acid (0.05 M) to the water (Gangstad and Nenseter, 2014), since it protonates the amines converting them into their corresponding ammonium salts, which are non-volatile, water-soluble and chemically stable compounds, while reducing their adsorption onto surfaces due to their ionic nature and hydration shell in aqueous solution. In principle, all this ensures that amines are retained in the aqueous phase of the impinger and do not escape or degrade before analysis, improving sampling recovery. For that reason, it is also recommended to generate validation data on the sulfuric acid amine capture method under PCC

stack conditions.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Haydn Barros: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Richard Harvey:** Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Hannah Cheales-Norman:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Investigation. **Chris Dimopoulos:** Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Rod Robinson:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Haydn Barros reports financial support was provided by UK Environment Agency. Haydn Barros reports financial support was provided by 2023–24 National Measurement System programme (UK). Haydn Barros reports financial support was provided by European Association of National Metrology Institutes (EURAMET), though the MetCCUS project. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Annex

Table A1

Results for the blanks in the Liquid Sampling Method test [μg].

Specie	T1				T4				T7				T9			
	I1	I2	I3	PW	I1	I2	I3	PW	I1	I2	I3	PW	I1	I2	I3	PW
LOD	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.09	0.05	0.04	0.04	0.01	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.01
NDMA					0.10				0.06				0.08			
NMEA					0.07								0.06			
NDEA																
NPIP					0.13				0.052				0.05			
NDPA																
NDBA											0.06					
NPYR					0.33			0.11	0.07				0.10			0.03
NMOR					0.35			0.12	0.06				0.09			0.03
Vol [mL]	245	212	254	52	205	207	183	86	227	211	219	56	249	206	245	56

Notes:

- In all the tests I1, I2 and I3 corresponds impingers 1, 2 and 3 respectively, while PW stands for Probe Water (after washing probe and impingers) and TC for Thermo-Sorb cartridges
- All the values below the limit of detection were left in blank
- All the liquid samples were quantified in $\mu\text{g/L}$; however, the corresponding masses, expressed in μg , are reported considering the volumes used in each test
- All the Thermo-Sorb cartridges were measured below the LOD (0.004 μg)
- As discussed in the text, the nitrosamines in I1 shows remains from the previous tests
- Vol. [mL] is the volume of the water collected in each impinger and probe water
- All nitrosamine's analytical uncertainties are $\pm 10\%$ of the reported value.

Table A2

Test results 01: Liquid Sampling Method [µg].

Specie	T2						T3						T5					
	I1	I2	I3	PW	TC	Nom.	I1	I2	I3	PW	TC	Nom.	I1	I2	I3	PW	TC	Nom.
LOD	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.03	0.02		0.05	0.04	0.05	0.03	0.05		0.04	0.05	0.05	0.1	0.04	
NDMA	5.0	1.7	0.3	0.06	0.07	6.5	6.2	1.1	0.3	0.3		6.4	5.3	0.9	0.1			6.8
NMEA	5.2	2.1	0.4		0.11	6.5	6.6	1.5	0.4	0.2		6.4	5.5	1.2	0.2			6.8
NDEA	4.5	1.7	0.7		0.22	6.5	6.4	1.9	0.7	0.1	0.18	6.4	4.9	1.8	0.4			6.8
NPIP	5.0	1.4	0.2	0.11		6.6	4.7	0.9	0.2	0.4		6.4	5.1	0.7	0.1			6.8
NDPA	3.3	3.1	1.2		0.51	6.5	5.0	2.3	1.1	0.2	0.23	6.4	3.6	2.6	0.7		0.16	6.7
NDBA	1.7	2.5	1.3		0.86	6.5	2.8	2.1	1.4	0.1	0.47	6.4	1.6	2.3	1.2		0.45	6.8
NPYR	4.3	0.8	0.1	0.39		6.5	1.9	0.2		0.9		6.4	4.5	0.4		0.3		6.8
NMOR	4.3	0.8	0.1	0.39		6.5	1.7	0.2		0.9		6.4	4.3	0.4		0.3		6.8
Vol [mL]	237	192	246	32			237	192	246	32			197	235	238	113		

Notes:

- The acronym Nom. stands for Nominal Mass, corresponding to the amount of individual nitrosamine injected in each test.
- Thermo-Sorb values were originally reported as mass within each cartridge, the values were corrected by the used dilution factor, & then we represent the mass not captured by the impingers and potentially escaping to the atmosphere
- Some Thermo-Sorb cartridges were measured below the LOD, which varies with the volume passing through them
- As discussed in the text, the nitrosamines in I1 shows remains from the previous tests

Table A3

Test results 02: Liquid Sampling Method [µg].

Specie	T6						T8						T10					
	I1	I2	I3	PW	TC	Nom.	I1	I2	I3	PW	TC	Nom.	I1	I2	I3	PW	TC	Nom.
LOD	0.06	0.05	0.04	0.02	0.004		0.05	0.04	0.06	0.02	0.004		0.04	0.04	0.05	0.01	0.004	
NDMA	5.34	0.77	0.18			6.1	4.34	0.58	0.07	0.51		6.1	4.02	0.87	0.14	0.91		6.7
NMEA	5.34	0.93	0.13			6.1	4.56	0.77	0.11	0.45		6.1	4.02	1.17	0.22	0.78		6.6
NDEA	5.06	1.36	0.24		0.04	6.1	4.34	1.11	0.19	0.34		6.1	3.57	1.67	0.44	0.58		6.6
NPIP	5.91	0.64	0.06			6.2	4.79	0.51	0.06	0.68		6.1	4.46	0.71	0.09	1.36		6.7
NDPA	3.94	2.09	0.58		0.12	6.1	3.65	1.71	0.44	0.24	0.10	6.1	2.46	2.18	1.04	0.41		6.6
NDBA	2.08	2.27	1.09		0.35	6.1	2.28	2.03	0.86	0.17	0.04	6.1	1.09	1.77	1.60	0.29		6.6
NPYR	4.50	0.27		0.05		6.1	3.42	0.21		1.07		6.1	2.90	0.22		2.34		6.6
NMOR	5.34	0.34		0.05		6.1	3.88	0.28		1.22		6.1	2.90	0.24		2.79		6.7
Vol [mL]	281	227	222	85			228	214	278	76			223	198	242	65		

Table A4

Test results 03: Liquid Sampling Method [µg].

Specie	T11						T12						T13					
	I1	I2	I3	PW	TC	Nom.	I1	I2	I3	PW	TC	Nom.	I1	I2	I3	PW	TC	Nom.
LOD	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.01	0.004		0.05	0.04	0.05	0.010	0.004		0.05	0.04	0.05	0.01	0.004	
NDMA	5.07	0.54	0.07	0.35		6.2	6.82	1.78	0.09			7.4	6.14	0.74	0.07	0.04		6.1
NMEA	5.07	0.69	0.09	0.23		6.2	6.36	2.33	0.10		0.05	7.4	5.91	0.91	0.11	0.03		6.1
NDEA	5.07	1.01	0.16	0.11		6.2	5.00	2.96	0.18		0.15	7.4	5.68	1.25	0.19	0.02		6.1
NPIP	4.54	0.47	0.05	0.69		6.2	7.50	1.29	0.06			7.4	5.91	0.70	0.06	0.06		6.1
NDPA	4.54	1.55	0.33	0.05		6.1	2.73	3.81	0.36		0.47	7.4	4.55	1.76	0.38	0.01	0.08	6.1
NDBA	2.94	1.92	0.67	0.04		6.2	0.64	2.96	0.68		1.22	7.4	2.73	2.07	0.77	0.01	0.20	6.1
NPYR	2.14	0.15		1.77		6.2	7.50	0.53	0	0.013		7.4	5.23	0.38		0.12		6.1
NMOR	2.03	0.16		2.02		6.2	7.73	0.57	0	0.013		7.4	5.45	0.42		0.13		6.1
Vol [mL]	267	216	257	63			227	212	226	48			227	212	226	48		

Table A5

Test results 04: Liquid Sampling Method [µg].

Specie	T14						T15					
	I1	I2	I3	PW	TC	Nom.	I1	I2	I3	PW	TC	Nom.
LOD	0.05	0.04	0.05	0.01	0.004		0.05	0.05	0.06	0.01	0.004	
NDMA	5.75	1.46	0.25	0.10		6.9	5.72	0.87	0.11	0.08		6.2
NMEA	5.27	1.86	0.41	0.07	0.05	6.9	5.72	1.08	0.12	0.05		6.2
NDEA	4.08	2.43	0.84	0.04	0.15	6.9	5.47	1.45	0.22	0.03		6.2
NPIP	6.23	1.05	0.14	0.15		7.0	5.97	0.77	0.07	0.13		6.3
NDPA	2.06	2.83	1.81	0.02	0.52	6.9	4.48	2.01	0.44	0.02	0.10	6.2
NDBA	0.41	1.50	2.14	0.01	1.50	6.9	2.74	2.29	0.83	0.02	0.29	6.2

(continued on next page)

Table A5 (continued)

Specie	T14						T15					
	I1	I2	I3	PW	TC	Nom.	I1	I2	I3	PW	TC	Nom.
NPYR	5.27	0.36		1.00		6.9	5.22	0.44		0.33		6.2
NMOR	5.27	0.38		0.55		6.9	5.47	0.47		0.35		6.2
Vol [mL]	240	202	255	62			249	234	277	62.9		

Table A6

Retention times in GC-TEA.

Species	Boiling point °C	Mass g/mol	Reported retention time (min)	GC Column / Notes	References
NO	-152	30	< 0.33	HayeSep N, Q, R, S, and T Elutes near solvent front or air peak GC-TEA with FFAP column	VICI, 2025(consulted in October 2025) Feng et al., 2011
NDMA	151	74	4.11		
NDEA	180	102	4.98		
NDiPA	195	130	5.78		
NDPA	206	130	6.81		
NPIP	218	114	10.25		
NDBA	238	158	10.99		

Fig. A1. Synthetic (0.1 M sulfamic acid) nitrosamine traced samples analysed (GC-TEA) after different storage times. Normalisation (100 %) corresponds to the values of samples immediately delivered to measure.

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